

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Izzatullayev L.A.

EFFECT OF APPLICATION OF TECHNOLOGICAL FACTORS ON COTTON

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

2023/OKTABR

